

STATUS OF INSECT PESTS AND NATURAL ENEMIES IN ORGANIC MANGO ORCHARD.

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Abstract

The present experiment was conducted to study the status of insect pests and natural enemies in organic mango orchard during 2021 to 2024 at organic farm, ACHF, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari, Gujarat, India. Mango, *Mangifera indica* L is one of the most important fruit crops grown in southern Gujarat and data on insect pests and natural enemies was recorded at fortnightly interval from ten randomly selected trees during vegetative and reproductive phases. Higher infestation of mango hopper, fruit fly, shoot borer, leaf webber, gall midge and leaf miner were recorded, while thrips, fruit borer, mealy bug and stone weevil have a negligible incidence. Natural enemies like green lace wing, spider and ant were recorded during investigation. The data obtained are correlated with weather parameters as it play pivotal role on variation in population of mango insect pests and natural enemies. Hopper, fruit fly, green lace wing, spider and red ant exhibited highly significant positive correlation with sunshine hours while highly significant negative correlation with evening relative humidity. Fruit fly and red ant shows highly significant positive correlation with maximum temperature while leaf miner and leaf webber shows highly significant negative correlation with maximum temperature. Hopper, gall midge, shoot borer, green lace wing and spider shows highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature. Hopper, green lace wing, spider and red ant exhibited highly significant negative correlation with rainfall. The present investigation indicates the most active period of each pest and its relation with weather parameters, thereby we can prepare a schedule to manage the particular pest.

Key words: Status, Organic mango, natural enemies, correlation, weather parameter

Introduction:

Mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) is the most important subtropical fruit crop of India, it is considered as the 'King of Fruits'. The fruits are utilized at all stages of development i.e., from immature stage to mature stage. Mango is considered one of the most popular fruits among millions of people in the tropical area and increasingly in the developed countries, because of its delicious taste, its nutritive value, attractive fragrance, health promoting qualities and high caloric value; it is ranked as one of the good fruits in the international market. The major mango producing countries in the world are India, China, Pakistan, Mexico, Thailand, Indonesia, Brazil, Philippines, Nigeria and Viet Nam. India ranks first in production of mango in the world (Patel and Kumar, 2020). The major mango producing states of our country are Andhra Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Karnataka, Bihar, Gujarat and Maharashtra. The area under mango cultivation in India is 2296 thousand hectare with production of 21378 thousand MT (Anon., 2019). Gujarat is one of the important mango growing state of India and occupies 166.3 thousand hectare area with production of 12.22 lakh MT. Valsad district of South Gujarat occupies 36.4 thousand hectare area with production of 2.47 lakh MT (Anon., 2020). In India, key challenges for mango production are insect pests and diseases. The mango crop is attacked by about 492 species of insects, 17 species of mites, and 26 species of nematodes at the world level, of these, 188 species of insects have been reported from India (Tandon and Verghese, 1985). Various insect-pests of mango viz., hoppers, mealybugs, leaf gall midges, shoot gall psylla, fruitfly, thrips, leaf webber, stem borer (Patel and Kumar, 2020). Although, there is tremendous scope for enhancement of productivity of mango but various abiotic and biotic factors are responsible for lowering the productivity. Among the biotic factors, insect pests play important role in deciding the quality production and productivity of mango. Mango trees suffer regularly a colossal loss due to ravages of pests. The crop is attacked by about 492 species of insects, 17 species of mites and 26 species of nematodes at the world level of these, 188 species of insects have been reported from India (Tandon and Verghese, 1985). The seasonal abundance and distribution of the pests depend largely upon the prevailing environmental condition, as the pests multiply tremendously during favorable weather conditions leading to their outbreaks. Environmental factors also influence natural enemy populations such as predators and parasitoids either directly or indirectly (Thomson *et al.*,

2010). Mango stem borers, weevils, fruit flies, jassid, webworms, mealy bugs and scale insects are very destructive pests of mango (Chowdhury, 2015). Insect pest management is very important for the profitable cultivation of mango. Looking to the above mentioned fact, an experiment on "Status of insect pests and natural enemies in organic mango orchard" was undertaken.

Materials And Methods:

Orchard of organic farm was chosen to monitor presence of insect pests and natural enemies of major insect pests of mango. Data on insect pests and natural enemies was recorded at fortnightly interval from ten randomly selected trees during vegetative and reproductive phases. Abundance of insect pests and predators and parasitoids were recorded. The data on presence of insect pests and predators/parasitoids correlated with abiotic factors i.e. temperature and humidity etc. Observations of sucking pests were recorded as hopper population per ten inflorescence/ growing shoots or 10 sweeps were recorded. For mealy bug, number of nymphs/female adults on ten terminal twigs/inflorescences was recorded. For thrips, total number of thrips per three leaves from 10 growing shoots was recorded. For recording chewing pests populations, number of damage shoot/webbed leaves per twigs were recorded for leaf webber and shoot borer.

For recording observation on stone weevil, number of infested fruits out of 10 randomly collected fruits per tree. For recording observation on fruit fly install five methyl euginol traps/ hectare. The immature and adult stages of sucking and chewing pests along with substrate was collected and brought to laboratory and observed for emergence of parasitoid if any. During maturity stage of fruits, ten fruit fly infested fruits will be collected and kept in laboratory conditions to record parasitoid if any. Number of larvae/ adults of predators were recorded by visual observation.

Result And Discussion:

A Study was carried out to know the seasonal abundance and occurrence of important insect –pests and natural enemies of mango during 2021-24.

3.1 Seasonal incidence of important insect –pests and natural enemies during 2021-22

The data obtained are summarized in Table-1 indicated that hopper population was observed throughout the year. Average population of hopper was recorded as 78.72 ± 81.67 hopper/ inflorescence/leaf/trunk.

The incidence of hopper started from 31st SMW. The maximum incidence of hopper was recorded as 214.70 hopper/ inflorescence/leaf/trunk during 9th SMW. Hopper population was migrated from trunk to upper canopy as new flush and inflorescence emergence increases. Population of fruit fly reached to its peak at 19th SMW with mean number of 495 fruit flies per trap. Average Fruit fly population was recorded 180.92 ± 138.51 /trap. The fruit fly population most abundant from 2nd fortnight of March to 1st fortnight of June and then onwards started declining and found nil during 27th SMW. Leaf gall midge incidence started at 37th SMW and reach at peak level at 45th SMW with 9.80 infested leaves/ 2 meter twig. Average population of leaf miner was recorded as 4.5 ± 3.39 infested leaves/ 2 meter twig. Infestation started at 33rd SMW and reach peak at 39th SMW with 9.90 infested leaves/ 2 meter twig. Average shoot borer infestation was recorded 1.86 ± 2.0 infested shoot/2 meter twig. Maximum population was recorded at 49th SMW with 5.10 infested shoot/2 meter twig. Leaf webber incidence started appearing during the 31st SMW, the incidence gradually increased and reached to its peak at 51 SMW with mean infestation of 5.50 active webs per tree. The average population of leaf webber was recorded 2.73 ± 2.16. Stone weevil, mealy bug, thrips and scale insect population was recorded rear during the year 2021-22. The data on natural enemies indicated that predators like green lace wing, spider and ant nest were recorded in mango ecosystem, while no parasitism was recorded.

To know the effect of various weather parameters on the population fluctuation of important insect pests and natural enemies of mango correlation between them was worked out (Table 2). Hopper population exhibited highly significant negative correlation with Minimum temperature (-0.872**) and evening relative humidity (-0.703**), while significant positive correlation with sunshine hours (0.422*) and significant negative correlation with rainfall (-0.458*). Fruit fly exhibited highly significant negative correlation with evening relative humidity (-0.529**) while significant positive correlation with Maximum temperature (0.390*) and sunshine hours (0.404*). Gall midge exhibits highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.427*). Leaf miner exhibited highly significant positive correlation with evening relative humidity (0.494**) and highly significant negative correlation with maximum temperature (-0.626**) and sunshine hours (-0.641**). Leaf webber exhibit highly significant negative correlation with maximum temperature (-0.548**) and sunshine hours (-0.564**) however significant positive correlation exhibit with evening relative humidity (0.476*).

Green lace wing exhibited highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.841**) while significant negative correlation with evening relative humidity (-0.471*) and rainfall (-0.382). Spider exhibit highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.906**), evening relative humidity (-0.676**) and rainfall (-0.489**), however significant negative correlation exhibit with sunshine hours (-0.401*). Ant shows highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.607**) and evening relative humidity (-0.597**) while significant negative correlation with sunshine hours (-0.440*).

Seasonal incidence of important insect –pests and natural enemies during 2022-23

Seasonal abundance and occurrence of insect –pests and natural enemies of mango during 2022-23 are summarized in Table-3 indicated that hopper population was observed throughout the year. Average population of hopper was recorded as 71.81 ± 75.55 hopper/ inflorescence/leaf/trunk. The incidence of hopper recorded from 29th SMW. The maximum incidence of hopper was recorded as 215.00 hopper/ inflorescence/leaf/trunk during 9th SMW. Population of fruit fly reached to its peak at 15th SMW with mean number of 498.0 fruit flies per trap. Average Fruit fly population was recorded 167.84 ± 144.97 /trap. The fruit fly population most abundant from 2nd fortnight of March

to 2nd fortnight of May and then onwards started declining. Leaf gall midge incidence started at 37th SMW and reach at peak level at 49th SMW with 8.30 infested leaves/ 2 meter twig. Average population of leaf miner was recorded as 5.09 ± 3.34 infested leaves/ 2 meter twig. Infestation started at 33rd SMW and reach peak at 45th SMW with 9.20 infested leaves/ 2 meter twig. Average shoot borer infestation was recorded 1.98 ± 2.08 infested shoot/2 meter twig. Maximum population was recorded at 51st SMW with 5.50 infested shoot/2 meter twig. Leaf webber incidence started appearing during the 31st SMW, the incidence gradually increased and reached to its peak at 45 and 48 SMW with mean infestation of 5.0 active webs per tree. The average population of leaf webber was recorded 2.47 ± 1.88. Mealybug incidence started at 5th SMW and reach at peak level at 15th SMW with 7.0 mealybug infested penicle/shoot/leaves. Stone weevil and scale insect population was recorded nil during the year 2022-23. The data on natural enemies indicated that predators like green lace wing, spider and ant nest were recorded in mango ecosystem, while no parasitism was recorded.

Effect of various weather parameters on the population fluctuation of important insect pests and natural enemies of mango correlation between them was worked out in Table 4. Hopper population exhibited highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (0.897**) and evening relative humidity (-0.563) while significant positive correlation with sunshine hours (0.357*) and significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.357*) and rainfall (-0.406*). Fruit fly exhibited highly significant positive correlation with sunshine hours (0.562**) while highly significant negative correlation with evening relative humidity (-0.744**) and significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.467*) and rainfall (-0.408*). Gall midge exhibits highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.633**). Leaf miner exhibited highly significant negative correlation with maximum temperature (-0.553**) sunshine hours (-0.504*). Shoot borer exhibited significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.457*). Mealybug population exhibited highly significant positive correlation with maximum temperature (0.711**) and sunshine hours (0.561**) while significant negative correlation with rainfall (-0.396*).

During period of study (2022-23), green lace wing exhibited highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.873**) and evening relative humidity (-0.566**) and significant negative correlation with rainfall (-0.477*). Spider exhibit highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.894**) and evening relative humidity (-0.8584*) and significant negative correlation with rainfall (-0.436*). Red ant shows highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.527**) and evening relative humidity (-0.617**) and significant positive correlation with sunshine hours (-0.458*).

Seasonal incidence of important insect –pests and natural enemies during 2023-24

Seasonal abundance and occurrence of insect –pests and natural enemies of mango during 2023-24 are discussed in Table-5 indicated that hopper population was observed throughout the year. Average population of hopper was recorded as 70.48 ± 72.3 hopper/ inflorescence/leaf/trunk. The incidence of hopper recorded from 31st SMW. The maximum incidence of hopper was recorded as 211.80 hopper/ inflorescence/leaf/trunk during 9th SMW. Population of fruit fly reached to its peak at 17th SMW with mean number of 410.00 fruit flies per trap. Average Fruit fly population was recorded 152.56 ± 112.68 /trap. The fruit fly population most abundant from 1st fortnight of April to 1st fortnight of June and then onwards started declining. Leaf gall midge incidence started at 37th SMW and reach at peak level at 3rd SMW with 6.80 infested leaves/ 2 meter twig with average 3.39 ± 2.51 infested leaves/ 2 meter twig. Average population of leaf miner was recorded as 4.67 ± 3.16 infested leaves/ 2 meter twig. Infestation started at 35th SMW

and reach peak at 47th SMW with 9.20 infested leaves/ 2 meter twig. Average shoot borer infestation was recorded 2.05 ± 1.83 infested shoot/2 meter twig. Maximum population was recorded at 1st SMW with 5.10 infested shoot/2 meter twig. Leaf Webber incidence started appearing during the 33rd SMW, the incidence gradually increased and reached to its peak at 49th SMW with mean infestation of 4.50 active webs per tree. The average population of leaf webber was recorded 2.22 ± 1.44 active webs per tree. Mealybug incidence started at 49th SMW and reach at peak level at 15th SMW with 5.10 mealybug infested panicle/shoot/leaves. Average population of fruit borer was recorded as 1.10 ± 1.36 infested fruits/tree. The incidence of fruit borer recorded from 1st SMW. The maximum incidence of fruit borer was recorded as 3.50 infested fruits/tree during 15th SMW. Stone weevil, thrips and scale insect population was recorded negligible during the year 2023-24. The data on natural enemies indicated that predators like green lace wing, spider and ant nest were recorded in mango ecosystem, while no parasitism was recorded.

The effect of various weather parameters on the population of important insect pests and natural enemies of mango and their correlation was worked out (Table 6). Hopper population exhibited highly significant positive correlation with sunshine hours (0.655**) while highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.659**) and Evening relative humidity (-0.698). Fruit fly exhibited highly significant positive correlation with maximum temperature (0.782**) and significant negative correlation with morning relative humidity (-0.467*). Gall midge exhibits highly significant positive correlation with sunshine hours (0.612**) while highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.877**) and evening relative humidity (-0.749**), however significant negative correlation with rainfall (-0.456*). Leaf miner exhibited highly significant positive correlation with sunshine hours (0.556**) and highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.779**), evening relative humidity (-0.634**) and significant negative correlation with rainfall (-0.409*). Shoot borer exhibited highly significant positive correlation with sunshine hours (0.415**) while highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.919**), evening relative humidity (-0.620**) and significant negative correlation with rainfall (-0.398*). Leaf webber exhibited highly significant positive correlation with sunshine hours (0.514**) while highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.862**) and evening relative humidity (-0.679**). Mealybug population exhibited highly significant positive correlation with sunshine hours (0.565**) while highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.527**), evening relative humidity (-0.670**) and significant negative correlation with rainfall (-0.403*).

Effect of weather parameters on natural enemies of mango shows that, green lace wing exhibited highly significant positive correlation with sunshine hours (0.688**) while highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.816**), evening relative humidity (-0.825**) and rainfall (-0.512**). Spider exhibit highly significant positive correlation with sunshine hours (0.644**) while highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.754**), evening relative humidity (-0.774**) and rainfall (-0.507**). Red ant shows highly significant positive correlation with maximum temperature (0.605**).

Seasonal incidence of important insect –pests and natural enemies during 2021-24

Pooled data on seasonal abundance of important insect –pests and natural enemies of mango and their correlation with weather parameter during 2021-24 are discussed hereunder. The data obtained are summarized in Table-7.

Hopper:

Data indicated that hopper population was observed throughout the three year of study. Average population of hopper was recorded as 73.67 ± 75.45 hopper/ inflorescence/leaf/trunk. The incidence of hopper recorded from 31st SMW. The maximum incidence of hopper was recorded as 210.83 hopper/ inflorescence/leaf/trunk during 9th SMW. Hopper population was migrated from trunk to upper canopy as new flush and inflorescence emergence increases. In past, Rahman *et al.* (2015) showed hopper population started increasing from 2nd week of February and reached peak in 2nd week of March, fluctuating from 6-13 hoppers per panicle till 3rd week of April and decreased thereafter. Similarly, Pushpalatha *et al.* (2007) recorded the peak incidence of leaf hopper was noticed in March-April. It can be said that the present findings are similar to earlier reports.

Fruit fly

Population of fruit fly reached to its peak at 17th SMW with mean number of 463.33 fruit flies per trap. Average Fruit fly population was recorded 167.11 ± 128.77 /trap. The fruit fly population most abundant from 1st fortnight of April to 1st fortnight of June and then onwards started declining. Earlier, Sumathi *et al.* (2019) recorded higher fruit fly population from April to August and very low in January month. Similarly, Patel *et al.* (2018) showed fruit fly population higher from April to July in South Gujarat condition, which is in concurrence with present findings.

Leaf gall midge

Leaf gall midge incidence started at 37th SMW and reach at peak level at 45th SMW with 7.70 infested leaves/ 2 meter twig. Average leaf gall midge infestation was recorded 4.20 ± 2.81 infested leaf/2 meter twig.

Leaf miner

Average population of leaf miner was recorded as 4.75 ± 3.18 infested leaves/ 2 meter twig. Infestation of leaf miner started at 33rd SMW and reach peak at 47th SMW with 8.63 infested leaves/ 2 meter twig.

Shoot borer

Average shoot borer infestation was recorded 1.96 ± 1.92 infested shoot/2 meter twig. Maximum population was recorded at 1st SMW with 5.10 infested shoot/2 meter twig. Previously, Patel *et al.* (2018) noticed severe incidence of shoot borer on new shoot of mango during October-February. Singh and Kaur (2014) observed mango shoot borer were most abundant during October to November which is in close agreement with present findings.

Leaf webber

Leaf Webber incidence started appearing during the 31st SMW, the incidence gradually increased and reached to its peak at 51st SMW. The average population of leaf webber was recorded 2.47 ± 1.74 active webs per tree. In case of leaf webber, Verma and Singh (2010) showed similar results as present data, they recorded leaf webber activity in the mango orchards began in the months of June and it remain active up to the December beyond that the activity declined to zero level up to April. The pest activity remains at high level from September to December. The most active periods of the pest was from August to December. The most active periods of the pest was from August to December. Similarly, Kasar *et al.* (2018) recorded most active period of mango leaf webber from August to December.

Infestation of mealybug and fruit borer found rare and not constantly recorded, while thrips, stone weevil and scale insect population was recorded negligible during the year 2021-24.

Natural enemies

The data on natural enemies indicated that predators like green lace wing, spider and ant nest were recorded in mango ecosystem, while no parasitism was recorded.

Higher population of green lace wing was observed during November to March. Earlier, Anant (2016) observed the chrysopa during December to April which is in concurrence with present findings.

Red and observed throughout the year with higher population recorded during December to May. In past, Bana *et al.* (2018) observed the red ant during February to May with low population. Similarly, Anant (2016) reported red ant remained active during October to fruiting stage of the trees. Present findings are in conformation with earlier workers.

Spider incidence started appearing during the 33rd SMW, the incidence gradually increased but low population of spider was recorded. The average population of spider was recorded 1.06 ± 0.69 spider per twig. In past, Anant (2016) observed the spider during fruiting period with low population which is in close agreement with present findings.

The effect of various weather parameters on the important insect pests and natural enemies of mango and their correlation was worked out (Table 8). Hopper population exhibited highly significant positive correlation sunshine hours (0.582**) while highly significant negative correlation with Minimum temperature (-0.888**) and Evening relative humidity (-0.752**) and rainfall (-0.556**). Fruit fly exhibited highly significant positive correlation with maximum temperature (0.646**) and sunshine hours (0.595**) while highly significant negative correlation with evening relative humidity (-0.659**) and significant negative correlation with rainfall (-0.417*). Gall midge exhibits highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.706**) and significant negative correlation with evening relative humidity (-0.400*) and rainfall (-0.420*). Leaf miner exhibited highly significant negative correlation with maximum temperature (-0.548**) and significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.457*). Shoot borer exhibited highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.613**) and significant negative correlation with maximum temperature (-0.419*). Leaf webber exhibited highly significant negative correlation with maximum temperature (-0.542**) and significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.482*).

Green lace wing exhibited highly significant positive correlation with sunshine hours (0.513**) while highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.931**), evening relative humidity (-0.723**) and rainfall (-0.649**). Spider exhibit highly significant positive correlation with sunshine hours (0.595**) while highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.932**), evening relative humidity (-0.820**) and rainfall (-0.663**). Red ant shows highly significant positive correlation with maximum temperature (0.601**) and sunshine hours (0.741**) while highly significant negative correlation with evening relative humidity (-0.797**) and rainfall (-0.589**) and significant negative correlation with minimum temperature (-0.418**).

Conclusion:

Present investigation indicate that mango hopper, fruit fly, shoot borer, leaf webber, gall midge and leaf miner are economic pests of mango and have a higher infestation while fruit borer and mealybug shows negligible infestation, however thrips and stone weevil not recorded during study period. Natural enemies' viz., Green lace wing, spider and ant were recorded during study period. Weather parameters play pivotal role on variation in population of mango insect pests and natural enemies. Hopper, fruit fly, green lace wing, spider and red ant exhibited highly significant positive correlation with sunshine hours while highly significant negative correlation with evening relative humidity. Fruit fly and red ant shows highly significant positive correlation with maximum

temperature while leaf miner and leaf webber shows highly significant negative correlation with maximum temperature. Hopper, gall midge, shoot borer, green lace wing and spider shows highly significant negative correlation with minimum temperature. Hopper, green lace wing, spider and red ant exhibited highly significant negative correlation with rainfall.

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Table-1 Seasonal abundance of important insect-pests of mango (2021-22)

SMW	Month	Hopper (No. of Leaf hopper/Panicle or shoot)	Fruit fly (No. of fruit fly/trap)	Gall midge (No. of infested leaves/ 2 meter twig)	Leaf miner (No. of infested leaves/ 2 meter twig)	Shoot borer (No. of infested shoot/2 meter twig)	Leaf webber (No. of webs/tree)	Green lace wing (egg/larva/ pupae of green lace wing/ twig)	Spider (No. of spider / twig)	Red Ant (No. of ant nest/ twig)
31	July	4.60	150.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.40	0.20	0.00	0.40
33	August	4.50	110.00	0.00	4.30	0.00	2.80	0.30	0.00	0.30
35	August	6.00	180.00	0.00	6.90	0.00	3.90	0.50	0.30	0.20
37	September	5.90	165.00	2.80	8.30	0.90	3.70	0.40	0.40	0.20
39	September	7.10	141.00	6.70	9.90	2.00	4.20	0.50	0.40	0.30
41	October	6.80	130.00	6.90	7.90	3.00	4.80	0.70	0.90	0.50
43	October	9.90	105.00	7.90	7.70	4.00	4.50	0.90	1.00	0.50
45	November	10.70	95.00	9.80	8.00	4.40	4.80	1.00	1.00	0.80
47	November	18.00	88.00	8.60	7.50	5.00	5.10	1.40	1.20	0.50
49	December	23.40	92.00	7.40	7.50	5.10	5.30	1.60	1.40	0.50
51	December	93.00	85.00	6.80	7.10	5.10	5.50	1.90	1.70	0.40
1	January	109.90	88.00	7.20	6.90	4.30	5.10	2.00	1.80	0.50
3	January	178.60	75.00	6.60	7.10	4.10	5.40	2.10	1.90	0.50
5	February	155.10	72.00	6.20	6.50	3.30	4.30	2.10	2.20	0.60
7	February	204.50	88.00	4.90	4.10	2.50	3.50	1.80	2.40	0.60
9	March	214.70	151.00	4.70	4.40	1.90	2.00	1.70	2.50	0.70
11	March	209.50	281.00	4.30	3.10	1.00	1.10	1.80	2.30	0.70
13	April	201.60	325.00	5.00	2.90	0.00	0.60	1.40	2.20	0.90
15	April	178.00	450.00	6.10	2.50	0.00	0.20	1.40	2.00	1.00
17	May	119.70	482.00	7.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.90	1.80	1.10
19	May	116.50	495.00	6.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.90	1.40	0.90
21	June	68.60	385.00	4.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.70	1.20	0.70
23	June	15.40	188.00	3.20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.60	1.00	0.50
25	July	6.00	82.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20	0.30	0.30
27	July	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	MIN	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	MAX	214.70	495.00	9.80	9.90	5.10	5.50	2.10	2.50	1.10
	AV ± SD	78.72±81.67	180.92±138.51	4.92±2.96	4.5±3.39	1.86±2	2.73±2.16	1.08±0.67	1.25±0.81	0.54±0.26

Table-2 Correlation between weather parameters and population of insect-pest and natural enemies (2021-22)

Insect-pests	Maximum Temperature °C	Minimum Temperature °C	Morning Relative Humidity	Evening Relative Humidity (%)	Sunshine Hours	Rainfall (mm)
Hopper	-0.200	-0.872**	-0.055	-0.703**	0.422*	-0.458*
Fruit fly	0.390*	-0.243	-0.179	-0.529**	0.404*	-0.153
Gall midge	-0.093	-0.427*	0.161	-0.119	-0.114	-0.207
Leaf miner	-0.626**	-0.105	0.336	0.494**	-0.641**	0.245
shoot borer	-0.328	-0.228	0.180	0.200	-0.299	-0.046
Leaf webber	-0.548**	-0.072	0.264	0.476*	-0.564**	0.236
Green lace wing	-0.286	-0.841**	0.044	-0.471*	0.224	-0.382*

Spider	-0.122	-0.906**	-0.046	-0.676**	0.401*	-0.489**
Red Ant	0.193	-0.607**	-0.073	-0.597**	0.440*	-0.290

*Significant at 5 per cent level of significance

**Significant at 1 per cent level of significance

Table-3 Seasonal abundance of important insect-pests of mango (2022-23)

SMW	Month	Hopper (No. of Leaf hopper/Panicle or shoot)	Fruit fly (No. of fruit fly/trap)	Gall midge (No. of infested leaves/ 2 meter twig)	Leaf miner (No. of infested leaves/ 2 meter twig)	Shoot borer (No. of infested shoot/2 meter twig)	Leaf webber (No. of webs/ tree)	Mealybug (No./ Penicle/shoot/ leaves)	Green lace wing (egg/larva/ pupae of green lace wing/ twig)	Spider (No. of spider / twig)	Red Ant (No. of ant nest/ twig)
29	July	3.20	25.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.30
31	August	4.50	70.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.40	0.00	0.30
33	August	5.60	55.00	0.00	5.80	0.00	1.50	0.00	0.30	0.20	0.20
35	September	6.80	78.00	0.00	6.90	0.00	2.20	0.00	0.40	0.30	0.30
37	September	7.00	72.00	4.20	7.50	1.00	3.00	0.00	0.60	0.50	0.40
39	October	14.00	81.00	5.50	8.20	2.20	4.30	0.00	1.10	0.60	0.50
41	October	28.00	78.00	7.00	8.50	3.00	4.70	0.00	1.30	0.80	0.60
43	October	32.00	66.00	7.70	9.00	3.80	5.00	0.00	1.30	0.90	0.70
45	November	49.00	78.00	7.60	9.20	4.20	4.80	0.00	1.50	0.80	0.50
47	November	58.00	75.00	8.00	8.00	4.90	4.60	0.00	1.70	1.00	0.40
49	December	72.50	92.00	8.30	8.60	5.20	5.00	0.00	1.60	1.20	0.30
51	December	106.00	101.00	7.90	8.20	5.50	4.70	0.00	1.80	1.20	0.40
1	January	132.60	123.00	8.20	7.80	5.00	4.20	0.00	2.00	1.40	0.50
3	January	172.50	138.00	7.50	7.10	4.00	3.60	0.00	2.50	1.60	0.60
5	February	198.00	153.00	7.20	6.80	3.80	3.30	3.20	2.20	2.10	0.60
7	February	206.00	189.00	6.50	6.30	3.10	3.00	3.80	2.20	2.00	0.70
9	March	215.00	299.00	6.00	5.10	2.60	2.60	4.60	2.00	1.70	0.80
11	March	208.50	382.00	5.20	4.20	1.20	2.00	5.00	1.60	1.80	0.80
13	April	132.50	480.00	4.30	3.40	0.00	1.40	6.20	1.70	1.30	0.90
15	April	52.00	498.00	3.90	3.00	0.00	0.90	7.00	1.80	1.20	1.10
17	April	36.00	451.00	2.20	1.80	0.00	0.00	6.60	1.20	1.00	0.90
19	May	32.00	315.00	0.00	1.80	0.00	0.00	5.80	1.30	0.80	0.70
21	May	12.00	127.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	4.10	0.80	0.50	0.60
23	June	9.00	110.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.80	0.40	0.20	0.50
25	June	2.50	60.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.30	0.00	0.20
	MIN	2.50	25.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.20
	MAX	215.00	498.00	8.30	9.20	5.50	5.00	7.00	2.50	2.10	1.10
	AV ± SD	71.81±75.55	167.84±144.97	4.29±3.35	5.09±3.34	1.98±2.08	2.47±1.88	1.89±2.54	1.29±0.69	0.92±0.63	0.55±0.23

Table-4 Correlation between weather parameters and population of insect-pest and natural enemies (2022-23).

Insect-pests	Maximum Temperature °C	Minimum Temperature °C	Morning Relative Humidity	Evening Relative Humidity (%)	Sunshine Hours	Rainfall (mm)
Hopper	-0.357*	-0.897**	0.062	-0.563**	0.357*	-0.406*
Fruit fly	0.363	-0.467*	-0.237	-0.744**	0.562**	-0.408*

Gall midge	-0.372	-0.633**	0.122	-0.164	-0.052	-0.210
Leaf miner	-0.553**	-0.351	0.277	0.242	-0.504**	0.109
shoot borer	-0.374	-0.457*	0.158	-0.019	-0.107	-0.174
Leaf webber	-0.500	-0.341	0.227	0.207	-0.368	0.012
Mealybug	0.711**	0.155	-0.365	-0.345	0.561**	-0.396*
Green lace wing	-0.167	-0.873**	-0.008	-0.566**	0.334	-0.477*
Spider	-0.235	-0.894**	0.032	-0.584**	0.304	-0.436*
Red Ant	0.279	-0.527**	-0.058	-0.617**	0.458*	-0.368

*Significant at 5 per cent level of significance

**Significant at 1 per cent level of significance

Table-5 Seasonal abundance of important insect-pests of mango (2023-24)

SMW	Month	Hopper (No. of Leaf hopper/ Panicle or shoot)	Fruit fly (No. of fruit fly/trap)	Gall midge (No. of infested leaves/ 2 meter twig)	Leaf miner (No. of infested leaves/ 2 meter twig)	Shoot borer (No. of infested shoot/2 meter twig)	Leaf webber (No. of webs/ tree)	Mealy bug (No./ Penicle/ shoot/ leaves)	Fruit borer (No. of infested fruit / tree)	Green lace wing (egg/larva/ pupae of green lace wing/ twig)	Spider (No. of spider / twig)	Red Ant (No. of ant nest/ twig)
31	July	4.30	45.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.30
33	August	5.50	62.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.60	0.00	0.00	0.40	0.30	0.40
35	August	5.80	60.00	0.00	3.80	0.00	1.40	0.00	0.00	0.30	0.40	0.30
37	September	6.80	72.00	1.20	4.40	0.80	1.50	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.30	0.30
39	September	15.50	85.00	3.20	6.80	1.10	2.10	0.00	0.00	0.80	0.40	0.30
41	October	20.00	92.00	3.80	6.50	1.90	2.30	0.00	0.00	1.10	0.60	0.40
43	October	23.00	75.00	4.90	8.10	2.30	3.10	0.00	0.00	1.20	0.50	0.40
45	November	28.80	98.00	5.60	8.50	2.90	3.50	0.00	0.00	1.50	0.70	0.40
47	November	33.10	65.00	6.50	9.20	3.50	3.80	0.00	0.00	1.80	0.80	0.50
49	December	46.60	78.00	6.00	8.00	4.50	4.50	2.50	0.00	1.80	1.00	0.50
51	December	51.80	92.00	5.40	7.80	5.00	4.20	2.00	0.00	1.60	1.50	0.50
1	January	74.90	105.00	6.20	7.90	5.10	4.30	2.80	0.60	2.20	1.60	0.60
3	January	135.10	112.00	6.80	7.00	4.80	3.90	3.80	1.10	2.40	2.00	0.60
5	February	151.40	117.00	6.60	6.60	4.70	3.50	4.20	1.90	2.10	2.20	0.60
7	February	164.00	126.00	5.50	6.20	4.00	3.20	3.00	2.00	2.40	1.60	0.60
9	March	211.80	130.00	4.80	6.50	3.20	2.60	3.50	2.80	2.30	1.50	0.70
11	March	207.10	185.00	4.20	5.20	2.10	2.80	4.80	3.00	2.50	1.90	0.80
13	April	209.50	260.00	3.40	4.50	1.90	2.20	4.40	3.40	2.30	1.60	0.80
15	April	143.70	350.00	3.80	3.90	1.30	1.80	5.10	3.50	1.90	1.60	0.90
17	May	100.50	410.00	4.00	3.20	1.00	1.60	4.60	3.20	1.70	1.40	1.00
19	May	63.10	400.00	2.80	2.60	0.80	1.40	2.20	3.00	1.40	1.20	1.00
21	June	35.40	335.00	0.00	0.00	0.30	0.70	2.50	2.50	1.20	0.80	0.90
23	June	13.80	255.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.40	0.00	1.50	0.80	0.50	0.90
25	July	7.70	130.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.60	0.40	0.80
27	July	2.90	75.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.30	0.00	0.60
	MIN	2.90	45.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.30
	MAX	211.80	410.00	6.80	9.20	5.10	4.50	5.10	3.50	2.50	2.20	1.00
	AV±STD	70.48±72.3	152.56±112.68	3.39±2.51	4.67±3.16	2.05±1.83	2.22±1.44	1.75 ±1.93	1.1 ± 1.36	1.41±0.76	0.99±0.65	0.6±0.23

Table-6 Correlation between weather parameters and population of insect-pest and natural enemies (2023-24).

Insect-pests	Maximum Temperature °C	Minimum Temperature °C	Morning Relative Humidity	Evening Relative Humidity (%)	Sunshine Hours	Rainfall (mm)
Hopper	0.268	-0.659**	-0.023	-0.698**	0.655**	-0.368
Fruit fly	0.782**	0.270	-0.467*	-0.326	0.327	-0.239
Gall midge	-0.016	-0.877**	-0.118	-0.749**	0.612**	-0.456*
Leaf miner	-0.085	-0.779**	-0.046	-0.634**	0.556**	-0.409*
shoot borer	-0.284	-0.919**	-0.010	-0.620**	0.415**	-0.398*
Leaf webber	-0.155	-0.862**	-0.064	-0.679**	0.514**	-0.480*
Mealybug	0.356	-0.527**	-0.156	-0.670**	0.565**	-0.403*
Fruit borer	0.654**	-0.158	-0.301	-0.555**	0.547**	-0.348
Green lace wing	0.205	-0.816**	-0.131	-0.825**	0.688**	-0.512**
Spider	0.186	-0.754**	-0.108	-0.774**	0.644**	-0.507**
Red Ant	0.605**	0.085	-0.354	-0.322	0.291	-0.094

*Significant at 5 per cent level of significance

**Significant at 1 per cent level of significance

Table-7 Seasonal abundance of important insect-pests of mango (Pooled of three years)

SMW	Month	Hopper (No. of Leaf hopper/ Panicle or shoot)	Fruit fly (No. of fruit fly/trap)	Gall midge (No. of infested leaves/ 2 meter twig)	Leaf miner (No. of infested leaves/ 2 meter twig)	Shoot borer (No. of infested shoot/2 meter twig)	Leaf webber (No. of webs/ tree)	Green lace wing (egg/larva/ pupae of green lace wing/ twig)	Spider (No. of spider / twig)	Red Ant (No. of ant nest/ twig)
31	July	4.03	73.33	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.47	0.20	0.00	0.33
33	August	4.83	80.67	0.00	1.43	0.00	1.47	0.37	0.10	0.33
35	August	5.80	98.33	0.00	5.50	0.00	2.27	0.37	0.30	0.23
37	September	6.50	105.00	1.33	6.53	0.57	2.47	0.43	0.33	0.27
39	September	9.87	99.33	4.70	8.07	1.37	3.10	0.63	0.43	0.33
41	October	13.60	101.00	5.40	7.53	2.37	3.80	0.97	0.70	0.47
43	October	20.30	86.00	6.60	8.10	3.10	4.10	1.13	0.77	0.50
45	November	23.83	86.33	7.70	8.50	3.70	4.43	1.27	0.87	0.63
47	November	33.37	77.00	7.57	8.63	4.23	4.57	1.57	0.93	0.50
49	December	42.67	81.67	7.13	7.83	4.83	4.80	1.70	1.13	0.47
51	December	72.43	89.67	6.83	7.83	5.10	4.90	1.70	1.47	0.40
1	January	96.93	98.00	7.10	7.67	4.97	4.70	2.00	1.53	0.50
3	January	148.77	103.33	7.20	7.30	4.63	4.50	2.17	1.77	0.53
5	February	159.67	109.00	6.77	6.73	4.00	3.80	2.23	2.00	0.60
7	February	188.83	122.33	5.87	5.70	3.43	3.33	2.13	2.03	0.60
9	March	210.83	156.67	5.33	5.73	2.73	2.53	2.07	2.00	0.70
11	March	210.53	255.00	4.83	4.47	1.90	2.17	2.10	1.97	0.77
13	April	206.53	322.33	4.53	3.87	1.03	1.60	1.77	1.87	0.83
15	April	151.40	426.67	4.73	3.27	0.43	1.13	1.67	1.63	0.93
17	May	90.73	463.33	4.97	2.07	0.33	0.83	1.47	1.47	1.07
19	May	71.87	448.67	3.83	1.47	0.27	0.47	1.17	1.20	0.93
21	June	45.33	345.00	1.50	0.60	0.10	0.23	1.07	0.93	0.77
23	June	13.73	190.00	1.07	0.00	0.00	0.13	0.73	0.67	0.67
25	July	7.57	107.33	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.40	0.30	0.53

27	July	1.80	51.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.27
	MIN	1.80	51.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.23
	MAX	210.83	463.33	7.70	8.63	5.10	4.90	2.23	2.03	1.07
	AV±STD	73.67±75.45	167.11±128.77	4.2±2.81	4.75±3.18	1.96±1.92	2.47±1.74	1.26±0.69	1.06±0.69	0.57±0.23

Table-8 Correlation between weather parameters and population of insect-pest and natural enemies (Pooled).

Insect-pests	Maximum Temperature °C	Minimum Temperature °C	Morning Relative Humidity	Evening Relative Humidity (%)	Sunshine Hours	Rainfall (mm)
Hopper	-0.159	-0.888**	-0.010	-0.752**	0.582**	-0.556**
Fruit fly	0.646**	-0.165	-0.343	-0.659**	0.595**	-0.417*
Gall midge	-0.196	-0.706**	0.046	-0.400*	0.157	-0.420*
Leaf miner	-0.548**	-0.457*	0.285	0.077	-0.313	-0.033
shoot borer	-0.419*	-0.613**	0.115	-0.184	-0.015	-0.305
Leaf webber	-0.542**	-0.482*	0.228	0.041	-0.237	-0.110
Green lace wing	-0.138	-0.931**	-0.013	-0.723**	0.513**	-0.649**
Spider	-0.050	-0.932**	-0.084	-0.820**	0.595**	-0.663**
Red Ant	0.601**	-0.418*	-0.296	-0.797**	0.741**	-0.589**

*Significant at 5 per cent level of significance

**Significant at 1 per cent level of significance